

Reaction to Leiden Declaration FDO

The undersigned organisations all support the work towards FAIR implementation, important for science and the transition to a practice of Open Science. Significant effort has been put globally into advocacy, methodologies and technologies that support FAIR implementation in the last 5 years, but much still remains to be done. In some areas FAIR-enabling foundations are well established; in others consolidation is still required.

There are important cultural challenges that need to be further addressed, such as the awareness and community adoption of FAIR practices and good data management practices overall.

There are also more technical issues that need attention, such as the overall FAIRification of various research objects: from assigning and managing identifiers to describing them with shared common domain-relevant semantics. These are important, but only first steps towards making the data itself interoperable and reusable. There is also the challenge of applying the FAIR principles to other types of research objects, such as software. The Leiden Declaration on FAIR digital objects¹ confirms one of the current challenges in relation to FAIR implementation: machine actionability. It proposes a solution to this challenge based on FAIR digital objects (FDO). We consider it worthwhile to further explore FDO as one of the possible solutions.

Successful implementation of FAIR principles relies on the buy-in from all research communities². Therefore, a community-driven process is needed to understand the main challenges in FAIR implementation, identify suitable solution(s) and how those compare in respect of suitability for community implementation.

As organisations active in the Dutch research data field we are in a strong position to assist in this community-driven exploration process through the science domains connected to the three Thematic DCCs in the Netherlands.

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¹ Leiden Declaration on FAIR digital objects. Retrieved 14 October 2022, from

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1D8Qvst5-44tAlMOp-0WbzPNxPuEra34miAKGo3Zkbc/edit>

² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Six Recommendations for implementation of FAIR practice by the FAIR in practice task force of the European open science cloud FAIR working group, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/986252>